

Structure of Subatomic Particles from a Heuristic Point of View

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Abstract

A hypothetical model of the internal structure of nucleons, and the muon as a composite particle inside nucleons has been created. The muon mass served as the starting point for the creation of the nucleon model based on the principles of classical physics without using the idea of quarks and quantum chromodynamics.

The author conducted a detailed analysis of the decay channels of kaons, pions and nucleons, which allowed him to draw a conclusion about their possible composition and geometry based on the numerical characteristics of their masses.

Result: based on the analysis of the well-known rest masses of electrons, nucleons, pions and muons, mechanistic models of the muon, proton and neutron were created, explaining the difference in their properties and behavior in strong interactions from a heuristic point of view. The difference in the internal structure of a proton and a neutron explains the ratio of their experimentally established anomalous magnetic moments. Besides this the spatial structure of the muon provides an explanation for its anomalous magnetic moment. IMPORTANT! The idea of the existence of a bound state of elementary charges - dense charge-preserved state (DCPS) of matter or time-stop encapsulation (TSE) - was put forward.

Introduction

The presented structure of nucleons is based on the idea of the reality of everything material and the absence of everything virtual in the micro world. The first task was to select the most reliable basic criteria that could remain virtually unchanged in the process of improving the methods and means of measurement and new interpretations of the results of experiments. Such criteria include the properties of the most fundamental particle - the electron. Namely: mass, unit charge and spin. [1] Fortunately, these values have already been studied a thousand times and their values established with the highest accuracy. No matter how their meaning may change in the future, the relationship between them will remain roughly the same as today. We are accustomed to comparing all sorts of things, even incomparable ones, and to do this with the help of numbers. A comparison of the numerical values of the masses of particles already discovered experimentally gave the following results.

Methods

A pattern was found in the particle masses expressed in electron masses. Almost all of them had a common divisor - nine (9). It all started with the muon, which has 207 electron masses (m_e): $207 / 9 = 23$ [2]. For the proton ($1836 m_e$) it turned out: $1836 / 9 = 204$ [3]. For pions on average: $270 / 9 = 30$ [4]. It is important that this division has no remainder. For other particles (we will talk about them below), if there was a

remainder, it was always a multiple of the same nine: $1/3$, $2/3$. Of course, all of the indicated particle masses were found experimentally and vary in different sources by small fractions of a percent, but this does not fundamentally change the essence: nine is present everywhere. Subsequent investigations showed that the idea with 9 is not a simple coincidence, but that there is a deeper meaning behind it. As is known, muons have a unit charge equal to the charge of an electron or positron. Consequently, an odd number of nines gives a certain sign when added, plus or minus, and an even number gives zero, that is, zero charge. Accordingly, the nine itself (nine charges) always has some total sign ("+1" or "-1"), and depending on the filling scheme of the muon "cassette" (and this cassette looks like 23 nines lined up in one chain with an alternating sign - "+ - + - ... +" or "- + - + ... -"), the muon receives a certain unit charge in total. It is worth noting that the extreme nines at both ends of the chain always have the same charge sign. Opposite charges somehow stably coexist in a close union and strict order in a very limited space, without annihilating (like positronium). Let's say that this is a dense charge-preserved state (DCPS) or being in a protective (time-stop) capsule. Perhaps this is one of the still unknown states of matter. Now let's go back to the very beginning and look at the structure of the nine. The nine is presented as a conventional static and flat figure.

Fig.1. Nine unit charges in each nine-element formation.

As can be seen from the Figure 1, the left nine has 5 negative charges and 4 positive charges. The total charge of this nine is one unit negative charge ("-1"). Accordingly, the right nine has a total charge of "+1". It is also important to note that the sign of the nine is determined by its central element or the sign of the corner elements. Geometrically, the nine has central symmetry and consists of three columns or rows of three elements. These triple elements have the peculiarity of sticking together, but if one of the triples is forced to break away from the nine, it will always be from any extreme column or row. Thus, the remaining pair of triples will always have a total charge of zero, and the outgoing triple will have a unit charge. These are the same $1/3$ and $2/3$ of the mass of the nine mentioned above. The exact spatial geometry of the muon cannot be determined, but it most likely looks like a bent or coiled chain with tightly strung nines of alternating sign. Muons seem to have some kind of shell and freely overcome the entire Earth's atmosphere and, most surprisingly, penetrate even several kilometers deep into the Earth. And this depth of penetration is very likely explained by the strong shell or structure of the muon, and not their lifespan at near-light speeds. By the way, why then is the lifetime of high-speed (near the speed of light) pions in cosmic rays significantly shorter than that of the muon? The answer will become clear a little later. Quantum mechanics draws a diagram of the decay of a muon into an electron, one electron antineutrino and one muon neutrino. The decay channels of subatomic particles studied by experimental physicists gave us reason to imagine their possible internal structure.

As is known, the kaon and the pion were first discovered in cosmic rays [5]. The first thing we noticed was the pion, or rather its varieties. A charged pion has a mass

equal to 273 electrons, and a neutral pion has a mass equal to 264 [4]. That is, their masses differ by the same nine: $273 - 264 = 9$. And how many nines are there in total? The "+" (π^+) pion and the "-" (π^-) pion both turned out to be equal to 30 whole and 1/3, and the neutral pion (π^0) - 29 whole and 1/3. The decay of a charged pion into a muon of the same charge and something else neutral (muon neutrino/antineutrino) is known. Simple accounting gives:

$$30\frac{1}{3} - 23 = 7\frac{1}{3}$$

This seven "with a tail" $\frac{1}{3}$, in general, we believe, will take a central place in the entire structure and fundamental concept of all subatomic particles. It has not yet been detected experimentally, but we predict its existence. Perhaps it exists in a free state but hides under the guise of a photon or a muon neutrino. It is neutral (7 whole nines give a final unit charge of "-1", and a fraction with its charge of "+1" neutralizes it) and has a mass of 66 electron masses. Let's remember the muon cassette. It is part of a charged pion as part of its chain of 30 whole nines. π^+ has μ^+ , and a chain of 7 nines is attached to it, which has a sign generally opposite to the muon charge. In the pion π^- , accordingly, all signs are opposite. Therefore, the seven itself can have a different charge sign, but because of the "tail" it becomes neutral. We would call it auron (from "aurum" - gold). If only someone would discover it. But let's get back to pions. The decay of a neutral pion almost always produces two "strange" photons [4][6]:

$$29\frac{1}{3} = 14\frac{2}{3} + 14\frac{2}{3}$$

There are sevens hidden in it: $29\frac{1}{3} = 4 \times 7\frac{1}{3}$. But the most interesting part is yet to come. As we have already said, the mass of the proton is 204 nines. The mass of the neutron is accordingly $204\frac{1}{3}$. (By the way, $\frac{1}{3}$ is 3 electron masses). Judging by these masses, the proton must be neutral, and the neutron must have a single charge, but we all know that the opposite is true. What could be the reason for this? We assumed that in both of these masses there are nine chargeless electron masses (chargeless nine?). Removing them (for the time being), we get 203 and $203\frac{1}{3}$. Everything is fine now. Let's continue counting. In various kaon decay channels, three different pions often appear together [9]. Let's add up their masses, expressed in nines:

$$\pi^+ + \pi^- + \pi^0 = 30\frac{1}{3} + 30\frac{1}{3} + 29\frac{1}{3} = 90$$

There are also decay channels with a pair of neutral or charged pions. We thought, "why couldn't there be pairs of all pions?", i.e. $2 \times 90 = 180$. And then came the moment of enlightenment:

$$180 + 23 = 203$$

Results

And now we were ready to write down the formula for the structure of the proton:

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$$2(\pi^+ + \pi^- + \pi^0) + \mu^+ = p^+$$

Fig.2. Pion-muon formula of the proton.

Almost immediately, this construction acquired geometric outlines in my brain: in the very center, at the origin of coordinates - a positive muon, and around it - six pions, located in pairs along three coordinate axes. Having placed the muon in the center, it was necessary to give it a shape with perfect symmetry. Of course, it became a

sphere. We've asked ourselves before: "Why exactly 23 nines in a muon?" And then again we remembered the seven-auron. What if the muon is like this:

$$m_\mu = 1 + 7\frac{1}{3} + 7\frac{1}{3} + 7\frac{1}{3} = 23$$

So this is what you are, handsome! Three aurons plus one nine are like a cherry on the cake. Here is his wooden model, shown in Fig. 3.

Fig.3

This is the so-called pseudo-hexagonal packing of nines on an ellipsoid. Of course, the aurones are not quite flat, as in our photo, but they maintain the curvature of the sphere they form, although it has a slightly flattened shape (9 nines along the equator, and only 8 along the meridian). Consequently, the quadrupole moment of the muon will have a negative value of about $-1/9$. If the proton as a whole has the shape of a sphere and spin rotation, then it is logical to conclude that six pions form a sphere of a slightly larger size around the central muon and lie in one continuous layer one nine thick. By dividing this sphere into two hemispheres, we get three pions in each hemisphere. Since the pions have approximately the same number of nines (30), each pion occupies one third of the hemisphere. In the figure, we depicted one hemisphere, marking each pion on it in a different color for convenience. The neutral pion has 28 full nines and $4/3$ s gathered in two places into locks.

In the very center of the picture below (Fig.4) there is an unfilled "hole". It is possible that it is a weak point in the shell. Also in the picture there are 2 two-colored nines formed by three " $\frac{1}{3}$ ". The first one is between π^0 and π^+ and the second one is between π^0 and π^- .

Fig.4. Half-spherical shell development of a nucleon (e.g. neutron).

These are like triple locks that hold three pions in a coupling. There are the same locks on the second hemi-sphere. These locks play a key role in the safety of the entire system. An analogy from our life will do here, namely the construction of stone arches of bridges, gates or windows. The two hemispheres experience the force of attraction from the central muon. The loss of the "lock" nine or another critical point collapses the entire outer sphere-shell onto this central muon.

Experimenting with possible pion configurations on a single-layer sphere, we saw that the diameter of the six-pion sphere leaves a lot of internal space (a large gap) between the surface of the inner muon and the inner surface of the surrounding pion sphere. We decided to try a variant with a two-layer sphere. The inner layer was formed by two neutral pions (as two hemispheres $2 \times 29\frac{1}{3}$), and the size of this inner sphere (single-layer without gaps) was optimal (as far as we could visually estimate) for placing the central, also almost spherical, muon inside it.

Fig. 5.

Fig. 6.

Fig. 7.

The two left photos (Fig.5, Fig.6) show the phases of assembling the inner hemisphere from parts of one neutral pion.

The second, outer layer was formed (also without gaps) by four charged pions.

As can be seen in the right photo (Fig.7), two charged pions when approaching form a regular hexagon (60 whole nines, which proves the correctness of the hexagonal packing for the large hemisphere). And two, related to them, hooks of $1/3$ are shown by a red compound ball in the geometric center of the hemisphere. The position of the hooks is shown conditionally. In the middle photo (Fig.6), two extreme balls of the inner hemisphere, divided by a red line into three equal parts, are also compound. One third of these balls is not shown. It is "foreign", that is, it relates to the pions of the two outer hemispheres and thus connects the two shells with each other with a "mechanical lock" (4 locks in total), which ensures the stability of the proton.

As a result, we got two practically equivalent versions of the proton model from the point of view of strict geometric symmetry, beauty and harmony. We could not shake the feeling that the entire structure of the proton was a double protective (?) shell around the central muon, inside which, by the way, there was still free space, where something very important could fit, completely chargeless, requiring a high degree of preservation. What could it be? Maybe this entity is the source of the magnetic (?) field of strong interaction? Perhaps the answer to this question will be received in the future. But the question about the second version of the possible structure of the proton, when all six pions (180 nines) form a single-layer sphere of a slightly larger size, naturally led me to the thought that this is, most likely, the structure of the neutron.

As is known, the experiment gives for the intrinsic magnetic moment of the proton the value of +2.793 nuclear magnetons, and the moment is directed along the spin. The

magnetic moment of the neutron is directed opposite to the spin and is equal to -1.913 nuclear magnetons [6]. The ratio of the magnetic moments of the neutron and proton is: $\mu_n / \mu_p = -2/3$ (0.685).

Fig. 8. The arrangement of shells in nucleons.

In any case, the ratio of the magnetic moments of the proton and neutron (-2/3) proves their different internal structure, namely, the structure of the pion shells. If we assume that the nucleus and the outer shell mainly determine the magnetic moment of a nucleon, and that the nucleus (muon) is the same for all nucleons, then the difference in the values of the magnetic moments will be determined by the ratio of the areas of the outer shells of the proton and neutron: $120/180 = 2/3$. How did the magnetic moment of the neutron end up being the inverse of that of the proton, i.e., not greater, but smaller and with a different sign? If we take only the ratios of nines in the shells, then a possible explanation for this paradox would be the following: the outer shell of the proton (charged pions) and the inner muon have parallel spins (i.e., they add up), while the shell of the neutron and its inner muon have antiparallel spins (they subtract). Roughly speaking, they rotate around the same axis, but in opposite directions. At the same time, neutral pions do not participate in the creation of magnetic moment in either case. Thus, we have: $120 + 23 = 143$ for the proton and $120 - 23 = 97$ for the neutron. If we take the exact value of the nines instead of the rounded value and add the unaccounted no-charge nine to the final sum, we get: $1 + 121\frac{1}{3} + 23 = 145\frac{1}{3}$ for the proton and $1 + 121\frac{1}{3} - 23 = 99\frac{1}{3}$ for the neutron. The ratio of moments $p/n = 145\frac{1}{3} : 99\frac{1}{3} = 1.463$ (without taking into account the slightly reduced radius of the proton's outer shell). This agrees well with the known ratio of the magnetic moments of the proton and neutron ($2.793 : 1.913 = 1.46$)[6]. The order of error is $\Delta = 0.2\%$.

The radius of the proton's magnetic moment is 0.84 femtometers [4]. The radius of the neutron's magnetic moment is 0.89 fm [6]. There is nothing else to compare with, but we will try to somehow analyze these sizes. The difference in radii is only 0.05 fm. But what if we approach it from the other side? The surface of the proton's outer sphere is covered by 120 nines, and the inner sphere by 60. That is, the inner sphere, in accordance with its twice smaller surface, has a radius $\sqrt{2}$ times smaller than the outer radius. This is about 0.6 fm. For the surface of the central muon with 23 nines, the radius will be roughly 0.3 to 0.4 fm. Knowing the diameter of the sphere and the number of identical "balls" covering it without gaps, we can calculate the size of these balls (nines). We got a radius of about 0.1 fm. Of course, this is only a very rough estimate of the size. But this is not so important. It would be more interesting to know why the neutron is unstable, while the proton is stable. What role does the extra 1/3 of the nine play in the neutron instability and where can it be located among the other nines? Perhaps, near one of the "key" nines? Or maybe it is "smeared" over the

outer surface of the pion shell and with its "-1" charge neutralizes the "+1" charge of the central muon. By the way, the presence of a positive charge in the center of the neutron has already been calculated based on a number of experiments measuring the distribution of electric charge inside the neutron [6].

It seems to us that the main factor of neutron instability is precisely the larger gap between the pion sphere and the central muon. Perhaps, the muon, as a result of its spinor motion, touches the outer (protective?) sphere from the inside or is repeatedly pushed from the inside into this sphere and at some point hits the critical point - the key nine or "hole", which entails the destruction of the outer single-layer shell, consisting, as we know, of six pions, its decay into two layers - the inner one, consisting of $2\pi^0$ and the outer one - of $2\pi^+$ and $2\pi^-$ - and these two spherical shells "lie" directly on the central muon. Now the muon no longer has room to "dangle", and the entire system decreases in size, becomes denser and becomes a proton, stable and "eternal". The story of the muon dangling seems quite realistic, if we consider that the neutron in a bundle with a proton in the nuclei of atoms is very stable. This can be explained by the fact that the neutron is attracted to the proton precisely due to the mutual attraction (strong interaction) of their central muons, which means that these muons are at the minimum possible distance from each other, and the neutron muon is tightly pressed from the inside to its spherical pion shell, and does not dangle inside it.

It should be noted that pion shells have an ordered, fairly rigid single-layer structure that maintains their spherical shape, preventing their collapse under the influence of the attraction (strong interaction) from the central element of the nucleon. Therefore, the cohesive forces within and between the nines within each shell must constitute a fifth, super strong interaction, aimed at maintaining the shell's sphericity. A second possibility for this shell behavior may be the existence of a preferential distance to the central element of the nucleon for the shell, analogous to the existence of energy levels in the electron shells of atoms.

A neutron eventually loses its " $\frac{1}{3}$ " of its nine (beta minus decay) before becoming a proton, and this, as we already know, is two electrons and one positron:

This " $\frac{1}{3}$ " in turn also decays into an electron and, as physicists claim, an electron antineutrino, but we see that this is nothing more than an electron-positron pair, which is electrically neutral in itself. Or it remains positronium for some time, which again decays into its constituent parts or annihilates with the emission of a photon. And a photon is the same electron-positron pair. The cause of annihilation is the destruction of the dense charge-preserved state (DCPS) or time-stop encapsulation (TSE) (see above).

A small fraction (about one per thousand) of free neutrons decay with the same products, but add an extra particle in the form of an emitted gamma ray [7]:

Consideration of K-mesons comes down to the exact geometry of proton or neutron fragments. The mass of K^+ is $493.677 \text{ MeV} = 966 m_e$. $K^0 = 497.611 \text{ MeV} = 974 m_e$ [8]. The difference in mass is close to one nine. But the lambda hyperon has a mass of 1116 MeV [9] or $2184 m_e$ or 242 whole and $\frac{2}{3}$ of our nines. And this, by the way, is exactly 8 charged pions.

Discussion

The short lifetime of all newly discovered particles suggests that their significance and meaning tend toward equally small roles in the overall structure of matter in the Universe [10][11].

„The fundamental mathematical equations of QCD have been known since the 1970s. However, except in special cases, they can only be solved approximately. Even today, theorists are unable to fully calculate the properties of nucleons, even with the most modern mathematical methods and powerful parallel computers. The problems are related to the fundamental properties of quantum chromo-dynamics (QCD), the theory of quarks, gluons and their interactions“. [12]

More attention should be paid to the electromagnetic form factor, which will help us understand how the electric charge and magnetic moment are distributed in the body of the nucleon, pion and muon. It has recently been experimentally proven that light can be converted into matter. [13]

„Composite particles often have large anomalous magnetic moments. The nucleons, protons and neutrons, both composed of quarks, are examples. The nucleon magnetic moments are both large and were unexpected; the proton's magnetic moment is much too large for an elementary particle, while the neutron's magnetic moment was expected to be zero due to its charge being zero.“ [14]

How many simultaneous coincidences can be considered random?

1. Division without remainder ($207/9=23$, $270/9=30$, $1836/9=204$)
2. Mass difference between $\pi^+ + \pi^0$ pions ($273 - 264 = 9$)
3. Proton formula: $2(\pi^+ + \pi^- + \pi^0) + \mu^+ = p^+$ (i.e. $2*90 + 23 = 203$)
4. Exactly 23 convex symmetrical figures (for example, spheres) can be stacked on the surface of a larger spheroid (ellipsoid) without gaps.
5. The known ratio of the magnetic moments of the proton and neutron ($2.793 : 1.913 = 1.46$). The ratio of moments according to the hypothesis: $\mu_p/\mu_n = 145\frac{1}{3} : 99\frac{1}{3} = 1.463$ (the order of error is $\Delta = 0.2\%$).

Summary

Conclusion: perhaps a new look at the internal structure of nucleons and muons will allow us to solve some unsolved problems of modern physics associated with it and will give a new direction in experiments to identify this volumetric geometric structure and to explain a magnetic moment difference of nucleons etc.

This hypothesis is not speculative since it is based on experimentally obtained properties of nucleons.

This hypothesis may become the basis for constructing a new, simpler and more elegant theory of elementary particle physics. If confirmation of the existence of a particle with a different nature of interaction forces, which is the cause and the only source of strong interactions in the nucleus of an atom, is found, this will bring us closer to understanding the nature of nucleons. We mean the central spherical muon, or even something uncharged inside the muon that is its "heart". With its strong field, it attracts and holds the pion shells around itself. In addition, this field interacts with the same field of another nucleon in such a way that the force can create an effect of either attraction or the same mutual repulsion between the "hearts". Important note: The binding forces that ensure the ordered arrangement of nines in the nucleon shells take precedence over the strong interaction between nucleons. This interaction can be called super-strong, and it acts between nines in the interior of each pion. The electrostatic forces of the charges of the pion shells play a secondary role in this case. Perhaps future research in this direction will provide important adjustments to this generally balanced model.

Pions are indeed formed from cosmic rays, but their origin is misunderstood. In fact, pions are NOT "born" and DO NOT "arise" when protons interact with air atoms and decay. In this case, pions and muons are the proton fragments. The relatively long lifetime of the muon is explained not by its high speed (which is even higher by short-lived pions), but by its geometry and encapsulation. All types of neutrinos may be fragments of destroyed time-stop capsules.

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